

BorderForce

Flexible system extending automated border surveillance by increased situational awareness adaptable to uncertain times with unforeseen events

D2.4 – AI Act Compliance Report, PIA, EIA, and SIA assessments

WP2 - System Specifications, Design & Pilots definition

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document presents the outcomes of **Task 2.5, *Regulatory Sandbox for AI Act Compliance***, within the BorderForce project. It offers a first step toward evaluating the alignment of the project's AI development with the Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act), General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the broader ethical expectations set out in the EU's Trustworthy AI framework. The aim of this document is to assess whether BorderForce is technically and legally compliant while remaining actively committed to responsible innovation practices.

Given the high-stakes nature of border surveillance, the introduction of AI systems without ethical safeguards can lead to serious consequences. These include, but are not limited to, rights violations and discriminatory outcomes to environmental inefficiencies and loss of public trust (Rinaldi and Teo, 2025). Anticipating and addressing these risks early is key to ensuring that AI development does not increase existing structural harms or create new vulnerabilities.

Rather than treating legal requirements and risk domains in isolation, this report integrates three essential assessments: Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA), Social Impact Assessment (SIA), and Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), into a single methodological tool. This tool is guided by six principles grounded in legislation and standards. In addition, it provides a structured way to understand how AI technologies intersect with legal, ethical, social, and environmental considerations throughout their lifecycle

This report is primarily intended for project partners, technical developers, legal and ethics leads, and external reviewers. It provides a reference point for future assessments, a baseline for identifying areas of improvement, and a space for structured reflection on the broader implications of AI systems developed under BorderForce. It is also meant to serve as a foundation for ongoing monitoring. As such, this document supports alignment with future obligations, while enabling the consortium to proactively engage with challenges related to the responsible development of AI in the border surveillance domain.

1.2 Partners

Deliverable D2.4 was developed by ETICAS, acting as leader of Task 2.5. The document draws on input from several members of the BorderForce consortium, particularly the partners involved in Work Package 2 (WP2). Technical contributions were provided by the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT), Eratosthenes Centre of Excellence (ECoE), European Dynamics (ED) Hardware and Software Engineering (HSE), Securiton GmbH (SECU), Geosystems Hellas IT (GSH) and VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland (VTT). These partners contributed

to several sections of the deliverable, most notably through their responses to the questionnaire.

1.3 Definitions, Acronyms, and Abbreviations

Acronym / Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology
BMS	Biometric Matching Service
C2	Command and Control
COP	Common Operational Picture
DGA	Data Governance Act
DPO	Data Protection Officer
ECoE	Eratosthenes Center of Excellence
ECRIS-TCN	European Criminal Records Information System – Third Country Nationals
ED	European Dynamics
EES	Entry/Exit System
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
FTD	Facilitated Transit Document
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information System
GSH	Geosystems Hellas IT
HSE	Hardware and Software Engineering
LED	Law Enforcement Directive
MID	Multiple Identity Detector
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MR	Mixed Reality
OSINT	Open-Source Intelligence
PIA	Privacy Impact Assessment
PUC	Pilot use case

SECU	Securitron GmbH
SIA	Social Impact Assessment
SIS	Schengen Information System
UAS	Unmanned Aerial Systems
VIS	Visa Information System
XR	Extended Reality

1.4 References

Directive - 2016/680 - EN - Law Enforcement Directive; LED - EUR-Lex (2016). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2016/680/oj/eng> (Accessed: 24 September 2025).

Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI | Shaping Europe's digital future (2019). Available at: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai> (Accessed: 13 October 2025).

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) - Legal Text (2016) General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Available at: <https://gdpr-info.eu/> (Accessed: 24 September 2025).

European Commission (2019). *Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI | Shaping Europe's digital future.* [online] European Commission. Available at: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>.

Regulation - 2017/2226 - EN - EUR-Lex (2017). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/2226/oj/eng> (Accessed: 24 September 2025).

Regulation - 2019/817 - EN - EUR-Lex (2019). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/817/oj/eng> (Accessed: 24 September 2025).

Regulation - 2022/868 - EN - EUR-Lex (2022). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/868/oj/eng> (Accessed: 24 September 2025).

Regulation - EU - 2024/1689 - EN - EUR-Lex (2024,). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj/eng> (Accessed: 24 September 2025).

2. Deliverable description

Deliverable 2.4 “AI Act Compliance Report, PIA, EIA, and SIA assessments” led by ETICAS is a public document developed within the framework of BorderForce’s WP2. Scheduled for submission in Month 12, this deliverable responds to the work plan set in the BorderForce Grant Agreement covering WP2 Task 2.4. It reflects a collective effort across technical and ethical partners to evaluate the project’s alignment with EU regulatory requirements, interpreted, and operationalised through the principles of Trustworthy AI.

This document consists of the following sections:

- The Publishable Executive Summary which provides an accessible overview of the deliverable’s scope.
- **Section 1** which details the core technological components being developed in BorderForce, their intended functionalities, and their integration into the project’s use cases.
- **Section 2** outlines the main legal and ethical frameworks relevant to the project, including the GDPR, the AI Act, the Data Governance Act, and the Law Enforcement Directive, together with the Trustworthy AI principles developed by the High-Level Expert Group on AI. It establishes a six-principle framework across the AI lifecycle that integrates regulatory obligations into six practical areas: privacy, fairness, explainability and transparency, accountability, safety and security, and environmental sustainability. This section then introduces a compliance matrix that maps each legal instrument to the six principles, ensuring that all obligations can be traced back to one or more verifiable safeguards.
- **Section 3** presents a risk identification of the BorderForce technology and the corresponding mitigation strategies. The identified risks are mapped across the six-principle framework together with best practices relevant to each stage of the AI lifecycle that are used as benchmarks for evaluation.
- **Section 4** which presents the results of the questionnaire developed for this task. The analysis addresses the ethical and legal considerations across the AI lifecycle, and through the six-principle framework.
- **Section 5** which presents the next steps, critical gaps, and outlines actions to improve cross-partner coordination,
- **Section 6** which proposes further work needed to ensure sustained compliance as the project progresses.
- Finally, the **Annex** includes the full version of the questionnaire used to gather partner input, which serves both as an assessment tool and a resource for ongoing ethical reflection.

3. BorderForce overview

Before exploring the legal frameworks governing AI and data protection, it's important to understand what BorderForce is and how it works. BorderForce is a Horizon Europe-funded project, under Grant Agreement 101168316. It is designed to help law enforcement make better decisions about border surveillance, risk detection, and incident response. Instead of overwhelming officers with raw sensor feeds like unprocessed streams of data from cameras, radars, and other monitoring devices, the system combines multiple data sources into geo-referenced risk indicators. These indicators pinpoint what is happening, where it is happening, and how confident the system is in its assessment.

This section draws from *Deliverable D2.1 User Requirements and System Architecture*, which lays the foundation for how BorderForce operates. The system is built from several technical components, each with a clear function:

- **Mobile/Deployable Command and Control (C2) stations** are the first point of collection in the field, which integrates AI to detect persons, vehicles, vessels, animals, or drones. They provide real-time situational input to the wider system.
- **Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites** expand this perspective by covering wide border areas, ensuring that mobile stations are supported with broad, persistent imagery and contextual awareness.
- **Drone swarms** fill the gap in difficult terrain. Unlike isolated drones, they coordinate flight plans and maintain connectivity through a mesh network, extending coverage and relaying information when ground or satellite links are weak.
- **The autonomous wireless mesh network** ties the drones, ground stations, and command centres together. It ensures that communication remains secure, resilient, and functional even if a node is lost.
- **The Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT) module** adds a layer of context, scanning public sources (for example, weather alerts or local events) to validate or challenge what the sensors detect, so operators do not act on signals in isolation.
- **Data fusion engine** which integrates all of these inputs, from satellites, drones, command stations, and OSINT, at the feature level. It removes duplicates, merges signals, and produces geo-referenced risk indicators that are presented to operators.

Together, these components form a continuous chain: sensors collect data, satellites extend visibility, drones secure difficult areas, OSINT provides context, the mesh network ensures connectivity, and the fusion engine translates everything into clear, usable information. This interlinked architecture supports

effective decision-making in border management. This is anchored in lawfulness through adherence to EU legal frameworks such as the GDPR, the Law Enforcement Directive, and the AI Act, which guide data use and accountability in AI-supported border management.

To make the data collected by BorderForce useful for decision-making, the system organizes all inputs into a Common Operational Picture (COP), which is a shared digital map accessible both in command centres and in the field. This ensures that all teams, analysts and officers on the ground, are working with the same information. Within this COP, the system assigns each event a risk score. This score is calculated using the Common Integrated Risk Analysis Model (CIRAM), an EU framework already used in border management. CIRAM evaluates three dimensions: how likely an event is to occur, how vulnerable the area is, and how serious the impact might be. This criterion helps officers focus on the most urgent or high-risk situations rather than being overwhelmed by less relevant alerts.

The communication backbone of the system is handled by a Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) broker, a protocol designed for reliability in unstable environments. This ensures that data exchanges continue smoothly even when network coverage is poor, which appears to be a frequent challenge in border regions as outlined in D2.1. Finally, every action within the system is automatically logged and time stamped. This creates a permanent record of who did what and when, supporting accountability, transparency, and the possibility of audits or after-action reviews.

Having explained how the technical architecture works and how the system processes information, the deliverable turns to the Use Cases, which show how BorderForce adapts these tools to different operational realities.

3. 1 Use cases

The BorderForce project is built around four distinct Use Cases (UCs), each reflecting specific operational challenges and technological requirements in border management. These scenarios serve both to guide system development and to evaluate how the project's tools perform under real-world conditions. Based on the Grant Agreement, the Use Cases are categorized by type of activity (irregular migration vs. smuggling) and operational geography (large vs. small area). The following descriptions outline the context and objectives of each UC.

1. **PUC1 – Irregular migration, large area:** This use case addresses the surveillance of extensive land border regions, often comprising mixed terrain and minimal infrastructure. These stretches, typically segmented into 30 km zones, present challenges in maintaining persistent monitoring and rapid response. BorderForce seeks to enhance situational awareness in these

settings by deploying mobile sensing units and fusion technologies to track movement across wide and sparsely monitored areas.

2. **PUC2 – Irregular migration, small area:** Focused on known crossing hotspots such as river fords, bridges, and railway corridors, this use case requires high responsiveness and precision. These areas are characterized by frequent, rapid border crossings and a need for close-range monitoring. BorderForce addresses this challenge by concentrating sensors in narrowly defined zones, enabling detection of activity such as fence breaches or obstacle circumvention, and facilitating short-term tracking of groups that may split or disperse.
3. **PUC3 – Smuggling, large area:** Smuggling in wide areas often involves varied and unpredictable tactics ranging from drone-based drops and trained animal couriers to river concealment and terrain exploitation. In response, BorderForce enhances coverage using a combination of mobile command stations and unmanned aerial systems (UAS), while also integrating open-source intelligence (OSINT) to anticipate activity through indicators such as public chatter or coordinated misinformation campaigns.
4. **PUC4 – Smuggling, small area:** This use case targets specific spots where activity concentrates: improvised rafts on rivers at known crossing points, goods thrown from slow freight trains and picked up near the tracks, and short-haul transfers from heavy to small vehicles just past customs. These places are often forested, dimly lit, and hard to reach. BorderForce places sensors to watch a limited corridor, keeps short tracks of people and vehicles, and uses OSINT within a tight time and place window to catch public hints, for example online resale activity near the site or local notices that affect traffic patterns.

Taken together, these four use cases show how BorderForce adapts its tools to different terrains, tactics, and operational demands. They illustrate the system's capacity to integrate sensors, OSINT, and risk assessment engines into a single operational picture that can guide law enforcement in diverse and often unpredictable contexts. At the same time, they call attention to the complexity of deploying AI in border management, where the stakes are high and the margin for error is narrow. Because each use case depends on data-intensive methods and the fusion of multiple information streams, they expose the project to significant legal and ethical problems. Questions of data protection, fairness, transparency, accountability, and security cut across all scenarios, regardless of geography or activity type. For this reason, the next section maps the relevant EU legislation and provides the framework through which BorderForce must be assessed and governed.

4. Legislation and Standards Mapping

Because BorderForce integrates several AI-driven components that process personal and contextual data to support law enforcement operations, it falls within the scope of multiple EU regulations. Compliance with these frameworks is mandatory and serves as the foundation for public trust while preventing potential harm. To meet its technical and operational objectives responsibly, the project must incorporate legal and ethical standards throughout system design and deployment. Without such safeguards, in high-stakes contexts such as border surveillance, AI deployment risks enabling privacy violations, discrimination, and the erosion of human rights (Rinaldi and Teo, 2025).

To foster rights-respecting technical innovation, the European Commission has introduced a broad agenda to make Europe fit for the digital age. Central to this effort is the creation of an **ecosystem of trust** based on EU values and fundamental rights. The aim is to give citizens confidence that AI solutions respect their dignity and freedoms, while also encouraging innovation among businesses. In practice, this means that AI developed in Europe must be both competitive and trustworthy, while also ethical, and aligned with the public interest.

The legislative landscape that supports this ecosystem of trust includes regulations such as the European Artificial Intelligence Act, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and the Law Enforcement Directive (LED), among others. Each of these instruments contributes specific obligations, from data protection and human oversight to risk classification and redress mechanisms. Taken together, they form the legal backbone for any high-risk AI system developed within the EU. As a Horizon Europe project operating within this regulatory environment, BorderForce must integrate these obligations into the development of its AI-enabled border management systems. As such, compliance must remain a design principle from early-stage architecture to final deployment.

4.1 General Data Protection Regulation

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is the core legal framework governing the protection of personal data within the European Union. It establishes binding rights for individuals and corresponding obligations for organisations, ensuring that the collection, use, and management of personal data uphold the fundamental right to data protection. The GDPR is particularly relevant for high-risk AI systems, as it provides a concrete set of requirements for how data should be collected, processed, stored, and safeguarded. BorderForce activities involve the processing of personal data, which means that all systems and operations must comply with GDPR principles. This includes ensuring data quality, establishing a lawful basis for processing, applying appropriate data protection measures, and

addressing risks of bias, particularly during the data-centric phases of the AI lifecycle and activities involving individuals.

In practical terms, GDPR compliance requires careful distinction between various categories of data processed within the project. The following section outlines the provisions most relevant for BorderForce. While anonymised data falls outside the scope of the Regulation, many project activities involve information that can directly or indirectly identify individuals. In these cases, full compliance with GDPR requirements applies, including safeguards tailored to the sensitive context of border management.

A particularly important consideration for BorderForce is the processing of special categories of personal data, such as information revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious beliefs, health status, or biometric identifiers. As a rule, the GDPR prohibits the use of such data because of the heightened risks it poses to individuals. However, Article 9(2) sets out exceptions under which processing may be permitted. In addition, Member States may introduce further conditions regarding the processing of biometric data.

General transparency requirements (Articles 12, 13, 14)

Data controllers are persons, authorities, or other body which, determines the purposes and means of processing of personal data. They must provide any information relating to the data processing to the data subject in a concise, understandable, accessible form. In the context of BorderForce, this obligation becomes more complex due to the nature of the system, which operates in areas where there is limited or no direct interaction with data subjects. Still, Article 12 requires that transparency be adapted to the specific context. In this case, the project should prepare general transparency materials to inform the public about the system's purpose, presence, and legal basis. This effort would help ensure compliance with broader transparency obligations and follow the guidance provided in Recitals 60 and 62 of the GDPR, which support context-appropriate approaches.

Closely related to this are the obligations under Article 13, which specify the information that must be provided when personal data is obtained, including the identity and contact details of the controller, the purposes and legal basis of the processing, the categories of recipients, and the nature of any data transfers. In BorderForce, however, data will often be collected indirectly and often without direct contact with the individual. While this limits the feasibility of fulfilling Article 13 in its strictest sense, it does not remove the obligation entirely. To comply with the spirit of Article 13, the project should consider public-facing documentation that explains the logic behind any automated processing or AI-supported decisions, such as pattern detection.

Article 14 (a–f) extends these information duties to cases where personal data are not obtained directly from the data subject. In such situations, the controller shall provide additional details including the period of data storage, the legitimate interests pursued, the data subject's rights (such as portability, withdrawal of consent, or the right to lodge a complaint), the source of the data, and, if applicable, whether it originated from publicly available sources. The controller shall provide this information within one month.

Further processing activities

Where the controller intends to process the personal data for a purpose other than that for which it was obtained, they shall first provide the data subject with information on that other purpose and with any relevant further information as referred to in Article 14 (1–4).

This requirement shall not apply if:

- The provision of such information proves impossible or would involve a disproportionate effort, particularly when processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes, or statistical purposes (subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in Article 89 (1)).
- The obligation is likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the processing objectives.
- Obtaining or disclosure is expressly laid down by Union or Member State law that provides appropriate measures to protect the data subject's legitimate interests.
- The personal data must remain confidential subject to an obligation of professional secrecy regulated by Union or Member State law, including a statutory obligation of secrecy.

In such cases, the controller shall take appropriate measures to protect the data subject's rights, freedoms and legitimate interests, including making the information publicly available.

Data Subject Rights

Data subjects have the right to know whether their personal data is being processed and to access their personal data. This allows individuals to understand how their data is being used and to exercise further rights. They have the right to rectify inaccurate or incomplete personal data, to obtain the erasure of personal data, to limit or restrict how their personal data is used in certain circumstances, and to object to processing of personal data concerning them. The controller shall communicate any rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing. The data subject shall have the right to receive their personal data,

provided to a controller, and have the right to transmit that data to another controller. In addition, the data subject shall have the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing. Member States may adopt legislative measures restricting the data subject's right of access when a partial or complete restriction constitutes a necessary and proportionate measure per Art 15 (1).

Member States shall provide for the controller to inform the data subject, in writing of any refusal or restriction of access and of the reasons why, and for the possibility of lodging a complaint or seeking a judicial remedy. Member States shall provide for the controller to document the factual or legal reasons on which the decision is based. Some exceptions to these rights exist per Article 11 of the Convention 108+ for national security and defence purposes. In addition, per Article 14 of the Convention 108+ Personal data may be transferred across borders if done so in compliance with the Data Governance Act. When the recipient is subject to the jurisdiction of a State or organisation which is not party to this convention, the transfer of personal data may only take place where an appropriate level of protection per Article 14 (3) is secured.

Per Article 32 of the GDPR the controller and the processor shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure security when processing personal data as listed in Article 32 (1)(a) to (d). When assessing the appropriate level of security, the risks presented by processing shall be accounted for. Adherence to an approved code of conduct or certification mechanisms, as mentioned in Article 40 and Article 42, may be used to demonstrate compliance with the requirements set out in Article 32 (1). The controller and processor shall take steps to ensure that any person acting under their authority who has access to personal data does not process them except on instructions from the controller or is required to do so by Union or Member State law.

4.2 European Union AI Act

The Artificial Intelligence Act is the European Union's regulatory framework for the development, deployment, and use of artificial intelligence systems. It entered into force in 2024, becoming the first binding legislation of its kind globally. The Act includes core provisions which has direct implications for EU-funded research and innovation projects such as BorderForce, it serves as a risk-based AI classification system which outlines the prohibited practices and requirements for the development and deployment of AI systems. Since BorderForce will make use of AI systems it is essential to assess the applicable AI requirements for the project's activities.

While the AI Act will officially apply in its entirety starting from 2 August 2026, certain provisions take effect earlier. Not all provisions of the AI Act are applicable to BorderForce, but since they will enter into force during the project's timeline,

the BorderForce consortium adopts a forward-looking approach that ensures the AI systems designed, developed, and used in the project are and will remain sustainable. This section will provide an overview of the relevant articles of AI Act's focus on a selection of obligations most relevant to the project. The following articles are or relevance to BorderForce.

Guidelines for high-risk systems (Articles 5, 10, 14)

Article 5 (1) of the AI Act outlines the specific uses of AI systems that are prohibited, such as biometric categorisation systems, social scoring, and indiscriminate forms of biometric surveillance. While BorderForce does not intend to develop prohibited systems, its use of AI in surveillance-related context requires careful consideration to Article 5 (2) to (7) which pertains to using AI for surveillance for law enforcement and how to guide its use legally. These provisions restrict the deployment of “real-time” remote biometric identification systems in public for law enforcement purposes. Any such use must be authorised by a competent judicial or administrative authority, strictly limited in time, geography, and scope, and accompanied by a fundamental rights impact assessment as provided in Article 27. For BorderForce, this article is a reminder that safeguards for biometric technologies must be embedded from the outset and monitored throughout the lifecycle.

High-risk classification and annex III

The AI Act categorises certain AI systems as “high-risk,” either because they are part of safety-critical products or because they are explicitly listed in Annex III. BorderForce systems fall within several Annex III categories, including:

- Development of an AI system is intended to improve the result of a previously completed human activity (border security and processing).
- AI system is intended to detect decision-making patterns or deviations and is not meant to replace or influence the previously completed human assessment, without proper human review.
- remote biometric identification.
- biometric categorisation involving sensitive or protected attributes.
- AI used in support of law enforcement for profiling or investigation.
- AI used to assess risks related to migration, asylum, or border control; and
- AI systems intended to be used for the purpose of detecting, recognising, or identifying natural persons, with the exception of the verification of travel documents.

These activities carry a significant potential impact on fundamental rights and therefore trigger heightened compliance obligations. BorderForce must therefore be developed based on training, validation and testing data sets that meet the quality criteria referred to in Article 10 (2) to (5) and shall be subject to appropriate

data governance and management. Similarly, the AI systems shall be designed and developed in such a way as to ensure that their operation is sufficiently transparent to enable deployers to interpret their output and can be effectively overseen by humans.

The oversight measures shall be commensurate with the risks, level of autonomy and context of use of the high-risk AI system and shall be ensured through measures in Article 14 (3). High-risk AI systems shall be designed and developed in such a way that they achieve an appropriate level of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity, and that they perform consistently in those respects. High-risk AI systems shall be resilient against attempts by unauthorised third parties to alter their use, outputs, or performance by exploiting system vulnerabilities such as data poisoning, model poisoning, or adversarial examples or model evasion, confidentiality attacks, or model flaws.

4.3 Data Governance Act

The Data Governance Act lays down the conditions for the re-use, within the EU, of certain categories of data held by public sector bodies. This Regulation does not create any obligation on public sector bodies to allow the re-use of data, nor does it release public sector bodies from their confidentiality obligations under EU or national law. While BorderForce does not seek to enable third-party data reuse, Article 5 offers helpful benchmarks to safeguarding the integrity of sensitive datasets that could be used for testing. As such, Article 5 is particularly relevant, as it introduces requirements of transparency, proportionality, and the protection of third-party rights in relation to the re-use of sensitive datasets, including those that are non-personal under Article 5(2). These provisions provide reference points for ensuring that data used for testing or evaluation within the project cannot be repurposed in ways that risk re-identification or unintended harm. Articles 5(4) to (14) further set out the conditions and procedures governing such re-use, which serve as practical safeguards for the project's data governance practices.

In addition, Article 7 establishes competent authorities to grant access to data categories referred to in Article 3 and to monitor compliance by data intermediation service providers. For BorderForce, this framework establishes the importance of accountability mechanisms and oversight functions, even when working with datasets that fall outside of the scope of personal data. This regulation remains important as it strengthens its approach to data integrity, and security across its lifecycle.

4.4 Law Enforcement Directive

This directive pertains to the protection of people when processing personal data for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data. It also regulates the free movement of such data between competent

authorities within the EU. Under the Directive, processing is lawful only when it is strictly necessary for the performance of a task carried out by a competent authority and is grounded in Union or Member State law (Article 1).

Safeguards for sensitive data

The Directive places particular emphasis on the handling of personal data that reveals protected characteristics or that uniquely identifies an individual. According to Article 10, such processing is permitted only in situations of strict necessity, and always with safeguards to protect the rights of the data subject. This includes additional obligations to inform individuals under Article 13, where controllers must provide clear information on the processing of their data, including its purposes, legal basis, and retention periods. In specific cases, controllers are also required to provide further details to enable individuals to exercise their rights.

Controllers are required to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure compliance with data protection principles, such as data minimisation, purpose limitation, and accuracy. These measures may include pseudonymisation, strong access controls, and safeguards that ensure only the data necessary for a specific purpose is processed. Furthermore, if a planned processing activity is likely to pose a high risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals, the Directive obliges the controller to conduct a prior impact assessment.

The Directive highlights the limits of lawful data processing, requiring the consortium to demonstrate strict necessity, proportionality, and safeguards when working with biometric or migration-related data. BorderForce must therefore ensure that:

- Only data necessary for the specific law enforcement purpose is processed.
- Sensitive categories of data are subject to heightened protections.
- Technical and organisational measures such as pseudonymisation and robust access control are integrated into system design.

In practice, this means that BorderForce cannot rely solely on GDPR principles but must also align with the stricter safeguards of the LED. This dual compliance approach ensures that the project remains lawful and legitimate when supporting activities that intersect with law enforcement functions.

4.5 Trustworthy AI principles

The idea of Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence emerged from the European Commission's attempt to shape a human-centric approach to AI. In 2018, the Commission launched an open consultation that laid the groundwork for the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. The following year, the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG), made up of academics, civil society representatives, and industry experts, published the guidelines. Since then, they have become an

important reference for EU AI policy and a global reference point in debates on responsible AI governance.

According to the HLEG, Trustworthy AI is defined by a set of requirements that ensure AI is lawful, ethical, and robust. These three conditions are mutually reinforcing: lawfulness ensures compliance with existing regulations, ethics anchors AI in values such as human dignity and justice, and robustness guarantees that systems function reliably and safely across their lifecycle. To put this vision into practice, the guidelines outline key requirements (HLEG, 2019):

1. **Privacy and data governance:** Requires full respect for privacy and data protection as well as appropriate data governance mechanisms that covers the quality and integrity of the data used. AI systems must guarantee privacy and data protection throughout a system's entire lifecycle.
2. **Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness:** Identifiable and discriminatory bias should be removed from data sets where possible. The way in which AI systems are developed may also suffer from unfair bias which must be addressed through oversight processes to analyse and address the system's purpose, constraints, requirements and decisions in a clear and transparent manner. In cases where BorderForce or its partners rely on pre-trained or third-party models and direct access to training data is not possible, fairness must be verified through performance testing and bias evaluation at the model and output levels. If bias is detected and cannot be mitigated or justified under lawful and proportionate use, the model's deployment should be reconsidered and subject to further review before operational use.
3. **Human agency and oversight:** AI systems should empower human beings, allowing them to make informed decisions and fostering their fundamental rights. At the same time, proper oversight mechanisms need to be ensured, which can be achieved through human-in-the-loop, human-on-the-loop, and human-in-command approaches.
4. **Transparency:** It should be possible to understand decisions made by an AI system for human beings, and to demand a suitable explanation of the AI system's decision-making process. Such explanation should be timely and adapted to the expertise of the stakeholder concerned. Explanations of how an AI system influences and shapes the organisational decision-making process, design choices of the system, and the rationale for deploying it, should be available.
5. **Accountability:** Mechanisms should be put in place to ensure responsibility and accountability for AI systems and their outcomes, both before and after their development. Due protection must be available for whistle-blowers when reporting legitimate concerns about an AI system.
6. **Technical robustness and safety:** AI systems should be developed with a preventative approach to risks and in a manner such that they reliably behave as intended while minimising unintentional and unexpected harm.

This should also apply to potential changes in their operating environment or the presence of other agents (human and artificial) that may interact with the system in an adversarial manner. AI systems should be protected against vulnerabilities that can allow them to be exploited by adversaries.

7. **Societal and environmental well-being:** AI systems must operate in the most environmentally friendly way possible throughout the system's development, deployment and use process, as well as its entire supply chain. Measures securing the environmental friendliness of AI systems' entire supply chain should be encouraged.

4.6 Matrix for compliance of trustworthy AI

Given the multiplicity of ethical and legal instruments that regulate AI in the EU, ensuring compliance under a single framework is challenging. In the effort to work effectively across intersecting frameworks (binding legislation, policy guidelines, and emerging standards), Eticas applies a harmonising framework based on six principles of Trustworthy AI: **privacy, fairness, explainability & transparency, accountability, safety & security, and environmental sustainability**. This structure reflects the project's evolving understanding of what responsible AI entails in practice. While the original HLEG framework includes human agency and oversight as a distinct dimension, in the BorderForce context these concerns are operationalised through accountability and transparency, which more directly capture the mechanisms available to law enforcement and system operators.

Building on this framework, Eticas developed a questionnaire (found on Annex I) that guided project partners in evaluating their activities against the six principles across the AI lifecycle. The questionnaire encouraged each partner to reflect on their system's alignment with ethical and legal expectations through practical, context-specific questions. Once completed, the responses were analysed and compared against best practices in each category, identifying both strengths and areas requiring further mitigation.

In this sense, the establishment of a framework that spans the AI lifecycle and is structured around the six principles serves as a cross-cutting structure as it integrates the binding requirements of existing EU legislation with standards. Rather than approaching the PIA, SIA, and EIA as parallel tracks, the questionnaire aims to reflect the interdependencies between them. Specific sections and questions within the questionnaire map onto the different dimensions of the three impact assessments as follows:

- **PIA elements** are addressed through questions related to data protection, legal basis, biometric data processing, data minimisation, user consent, anonymisation, access rights, and storage. These are aligned with GDPR, the Law Enforcement Directive, and the AI Act.

- **SIA elements** are embedded in questions exploring the social effects of the technology, such as discriminatory impact, power imbalances, stakeholder exclusion, public trust, and redress mechanisms. These aim to capture risks to rights, freedoms, and societal cohesion, particularly when systems are used in contexts marked by migration, marginalisation, or surveillance.
- **EIA elements** are reflected in questions about computational resources, training demands, model architecture, and environmental performance trade-offs. While less developed in AI regulation, these concerns are central to ensuring that digital innovation is aligned with the EU's green and digital transitions.

Building on this framework, the deliverable introduces a compliance matrix that maps each legal instrument to the six principles, ensuring that all obligations can be traced back to one or more verifiable safeguards.

Table 1. Matrix of compliance with regional legislation

Category	Requirement	GDPR	AI Act	Law Enforcement Directive	Regulation (EU) 2019/817
Privacy	<p>Integrate data minimization and pseudonymization to ensure that only the minimum necessary personal data (e.g. images, biometrics) are collected, processed, and stored, and that privacy safeguards are active by default such as strict access controls and automatic anonymization of stored footage. Personal data must be kept accurate and up to date, with mechanisms for correcting errors (e.g., misidentified individuals) and preventing false matches that could unfairly flag individuals.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art. 5(1)(c) and Art. 25: embed privacy-by-design measures that limit data collection and processing to what is strictly necessary. • Art. 32: implement safeguards through pseudonymisation, access controls, and anonymisation, reducing risks of misuse and improving system efficiency. • Articles 5(1)(d) and 16 require data shall be kept up to date and accurate and subjects have the right to rectification. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Article 10: sets rules for training, validation, and testing data, including quality, bias mitigation, and governance of datasets. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Article 4(1)(a–e): personal data must be processed lawfully, fairly, collected for specified purposes, limited to what is necessary, accurate, and stored no longer than required. • Article 8 – 10: Processing must have a clear legal basis in Union or Member State law. Special categories of data (including biometric and genetic data) may only be processed when strictly necessary, authorised by law, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art. 17–20: Data protection principles (purpose limitation, access control, logging). • Art. 28–30: Data security and protection obligations.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Article 12 ensures that information about data processing must be provided to the subject in an easy-to-understand form. 		<p>and safeguarded by appropriate measures.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Articles 24–25: Controllers must implement data protection by design and by default, ensuring technical and organisational measures secure the processing throughout the lifecycle. 	
<p>Explainability & Transparency</p>	<p>System outputs must be interpretable, including reasons for alerts, classifications, or risk scores. Bias audits must be conducted. Log all AI decisions with metadata including timestamps, sensor data, model version, and operator review status.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Articles 5(1)(d) and 16: data shall be kept up to date and accurate and subjects have the right to rectification. Article 12: processing must be provided to the subject in an easy-to-understand form. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Art. 13 and 50: support human understanding and decision-making, particularly in high-stakes operational contexts. Art. 12: mandates record-keeping and logging to ensure auditability and enable incident reconstruction. This 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Articles 13 and 14: require controllers to inform data subjects about the collection and processing of their personal data, even when obtained indirectly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Arts. 44–46: Logging obligations ensure traceability of system use, but no transparency or explainability of outputs to users or individuals.

			<p>facilitates effective post-deployment oversight and accountability.</p>		
<p>Safety & Security</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art. 32 mandates that the controller and the processor shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure security when processing personal data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art. 5 (1): outlines the specific uses of AI systems that are prohibited. BorderForce must be developed based on training, validation and testing data sets that meet the criteria in Article 10 (2) to (5) • Art 14 outlines the oversight measures for using high-risk AI systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art. 10 mandates that processing is permitted only by necessity, and with safeguards to protect the rights of the data subject. • Art. 13: controllers must provide clear information on the processing of personal data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arts. 28–30: Define obligations on system security, resilience, and integrity of data exchange. • Arts. 38–40: Access to systems by national authorities requires authorisation and human verification. Oversight provisions are limited compared to AI Act.

<p style="text-align: center;">Fairness</p>	<p>Datasets used in model training and testing must be diverse and include metadata to enable bias audits.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art. 5(1)(a): Processing must be lawful, fair, and transparent. • Art. 9(1): Prohibits processing of special categories of data, unless with safeguards. • Art. 22 & Recital 71: Individuals have the right not to be subject to solely automated decisions; safeguards must prevent discriminatory effects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art. 10 mandates the use of representative, relevant, and high-quality datasets to prevent discriminatory or biased outcomes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Article 20: Automated decision-making, including profiling, that produces adverse legal effects or significantly affects individuals, is prohibited unless authorised by law, with safeguards to protect fairness and fundamental rights. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not referenced.
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<p>Accountability</p>	<p>Ensure all AI-driven decisions are reviewed by a human and can be overridden if necessary. review status. This means every scan or alert should be recorded (with timestamps, sensor data, AI outputs, etc.) so that auditors or authorities can later trace how a decision was made.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art. 22, protects individuals from decisions based solely on automated processing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art. 14 requires effective human oversight to ensure accountability and prevent overreliance on automated decisions. • Recital 71: Requires meaningful human intervention, allowing individuals to contest decisions and ensuring oversight of automated processing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Article 30: Supervisory authorities must be able to access records and documentation to verify compliance, which reinforces the controller's accountability obligations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arts. 37 & 47: Assign responsibilities to EU-LISA and national authorities for compliance; logging supports accountability.
<p>Environmental Sustainability</p>	<p>Not referenced.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not referenced. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not referenced. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not referenced. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not referenced.

The compliance matrix consolidates the obligations arising from the EU’s legislation and aligns them with the operational categories of Eticas’ 6-principle framework. While the environmental dimension is not explicitly defined in the current legislative backbone, it remains a core aspect of Trustworthy AI and will be considered through sustainability-oriented design principles and monitoring practices.

5. Risk Identification and Mitigation Measures

While legislation establishes the obligations that govern BorderForce, compliance depends on identifying concrete points in system design and deployment where risks may arise. Because the project integrates AI, surveillance tools, and sensitive data, it faces challenges across multiple dimensions. Addressing these requires a structured risk analysis paired with mitigation strategies. The next section examines these risks in detail and outlines the safeguards needed to ensure alignment with the AI Act, the GDPR, and the wider EU framework for Trustworthy AI.

BorderForce’s role as a multi-sensor surveillance platform places it in the high-risk category under the AI Act (Article 6, Annex III), given its use in law enforcement and border control. This classification imposes strict obligations throughout the AI lifecycle, including requirements on data protection, robustness, and oversight.

The risk and mitigation strategy presented here is organised around the 6 principles of privacy, fairness, transparency, accountability, safety and security, and environmental sustainability. In practice, these principles often overlap, and safeguards that address one dimension can reinforce others. The benchmarks applied therefore draw on binding obligations under EU law (AI Act, GDPR, LED) and the ethical framework developed by the HLEG. Together, these elements form the basis for the impact assessment, which evaluates BorderForce’s practices using evidence gathered through partner questionnaires.

Table 2. Risk identification and mitigation measures

Principles	BorderForce Risk Identification and Mitigation Measures
Privacy	Risk: BorderForce collects and fuses data from drones, satellites, mobile units, and OSINT, which makes the processing personal and biometric data likely. The resulting risks relate not to the processing itself but to how such data is collected, stored, and used, particularly where safeguards are inadequate or poorly enforced. Even when the system does not aim to identify individuals, visual data can render them identifiable,

	<p>triggering GDPR Articles 4 and 9 obligations. Without a clearly defined lawful basis under Article 6 GDPR and Article 8 LED, data collection risks being excessive and unjustified. Additionally, weak filtering of OSINT sources that might capture personal identifiers, poor data quality checks that compromise reliability, and inadequate retention or deletion practices undermine accountability.</p> <p>Good practice mitigations across the lifecycle to address risks identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Pre-processing: Privacy requires a clearly defined lawful basis for each category of data collected, with particular attention to sensitive or biometric information. Collection parameters should be narrowly scoped to what is strictly necessary for border risk detection, supported by safeguards such as pseudonymisation, or the use of synthetic datasets where possible. When OSINT sources are used, privacy risks must be mitigated through filtering mechanisms that limit the capture of personal identifiers, whether through automated PII detection or carefully curated inputs.● In-processing: Safeguards must be actively enforced during operations. This means ensuring that minimisation protocols function in real time, monitoring the types of data being captured, and validating that information remains relevant and accurate. Safeguards should also prevent operators from bypassing restrictions or accessing data beyond their authorisation.● Post-processing: After deployment, the focus shifts to accountability and oversight. Privacy requires secure logging of all collection and processing activities, with audit trails that make compliance verifiable. Clear data retention periods must be enforced consistently, supported by mechanisms for timely deletion or anonymisation. Periodic audits and reviews are essential to ensure that the system continues to process only
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	<p>what is necessary and that data remains accurate and reliable throughout its lifecycle.</p>
Fairness	<p>Risk: The components may reproduce or amplify structural biases if data is incomplete, or not representative of the operational environment. This is concerning in migration and smuggling contexts, where systemic bias can disproportionately affect vulnerable groups. AI Act Article 10 (3) requires datasets to be relevant, representative, and free of errors, and demands testing for bias during development. If the fusion engine amplifies existing operational biases, risks of disproportionate surveillance or discriminatory treatment arise. Under GDPR Art. 5(1)(a), processing must also respect fairness, a principle that applies not only to data but to its downstream impact on individuals.</p> <p>Good practice mitigations across the lifecycle to address risks identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Pre-processing: Datasets should be selected and tested to ensure they reflect the diversity of operational contexts without systematically excluding or over-representing particular groups. Bias detection and mitigation must be integrated into model training and validation, with procedures to identify potential discriminatory outcomes before deployment.● In-processing: During operations, fusion and risk scoring must be monitored for patterns that suggest disproportionate impacts on specific groups or regions. Operators should have the ability to review and contest alerts if they appear biased or unjustified. Governance procedures should ensure that decisions influenced by the system are proportional, evidence-based, and not solely reliant on automated outputs.● Post-processing: BorderForce must establish mechanisms for auditing fairness over time, including logs of alerts and their outcomes, and periodic reviews of whether risk assessments correlate with biased enforcement patterns.
	<p>Risk: BorderForce outputs fuse risk indicators instead of raw feeds, which simplifies operator decisions but risks obscuring</p>

Explainability & Transparency	<p>the underlying logic. If officers do not understand why an alert was generated, automation bias could occur, with operators deferring to the system even in uncertain cases. The AI Act (Arts. 13–14) requires that users receive meaningful explanations, and GDPR Articles 13–15 require transparency about the logic of automated processing. Explanations must go beyond technical manuals, offering operators contextual information about confidence levels, thresholds, and sources, and ensuring external oversight bodies can review system logic when necessary.</p> <p>Good practice mitigations across the lifecycle to address risks identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Pre-processing: Transparency requirements should be integrated into the system design. This includes documenting the models used, their training data, and their limitations. Interfaces should be designed to surface key information such as confidence levels, risk thresholds, and contributing data sources. This must be done in a format accessible to non-technical users.● In-processing: During operations, outputs must be presented with clear indicators that explain the risk score and the rationale behind it. Operators should be able to see why the system flagged an event, what data streams contributed, and how certain the assessment is. Procedures should be in place to prevent automation bias, ensuring that officers can challenge or override the system where alerts appear inconsistent with the wider operational picture.● Post-processing: Transparency must extend to oversight bodies and audits. This includes maintaining logs of how risk scores were generated, enabling later review of decision logic, and allowing independent evaluators to assess whether explanations are meaningful and sufficient. Periodic audits should test whether users and oversight actors understand the explanations provided, and whether these support accountable decision-making.
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Accountability	<p>Risk: Strong accountability measures are already foreseen, such as audit trails, logging of operator actions, and time-stamped records of system changes. These align with GDPR Article 5(2) and 30 and AI Act Article 12 on records of processing. To meet compliance requirements, BorderForce must ensure end-to-end traceability of data flows and decisions, clear documentation of oversight points, and defined escalation mechanisms in case of anomalies. Without harmonised accountability procedures, system-wide governance risks fragmentation.</p> <p>Good practice mitigations across the lifecycle to address risks identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Pre-processing: Requires embedding record-keeping into the architecture. This includes defining what will be logged (data inputs, processing steps, operator actions), who has oversight of the logs, and how escalation mechanisms will be triggered.● In-processing: During operations, accountability mechanisms must function cohesively. The data flows, system change, and operator interactions should be time-stamped and logged in a secure and tamper-resistant way. Operators must know their actions are traceable, and procedures should define how anomalies or overrides are recorded.● Post-processing: Logs and audit trails must be accessible for review by both internal and external oversight bodies. Regular audits should test whether the records are complete, accurate, and usable for accountability purposes. Findings from these audits should feed back into governance improvements, ensuring that accountability is effective in practice.
Safety & Security	<p>Risk: The technical architecture (drones, mesh networks, central fusion, and OSINT) creates multiple attack surfaces. Risks include adversarial manipulation of sensor inputs, hijacking of drone control, or injection of false OSINT signals. AI Act Article 15 requires robustness, accuracy, and resilience against malicious use, while GDPR Article 32 requires controllers to adopt adequate technical and organisational</p>

	<p>security measures. Encryption, firewalls, and fail-safes provide a solid foundation, but they must be complemented with red-teaming, formal threat modelling, and operational stress-testing. Without these, BorderForce risks remaining vulnerable despite its design safeguards.</p> <p>Good practice mitigations across the lifecycle to address risks identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Pre-processing: Robustness and safety means adopting security-by-design principles, conducting formal threat modelling, and defining mitigation strategies for known vulnerabilities.● In-processing: During operations, robustness requires continuous monitoring for anomalies and active defences against manipulation. This includes intrusion detection systems, automated alerts for unusual data patterns, and clear operator procedures for responding to suspected attacks. Fail-safes such as drone return-to-base and mesh rerouting must be regularly tested in real conditions to ensure they function.● Post-processing: After deployment, robustness and safety depend on ongoing verification. Logs of incidents and anomalies must be reviewed, and red-teaming or penetration testing exercises should be conducted periodically to identify weaknesses. Audit processes should verify not only whether defences exist, but whether they are effective in practice. Feedback loops from these audits should inform iterative improvements, ensuring resilience evolves with emerging threats.
<p>Environmental Sustainability</p>	<p>Risk: BorderForce relies on energy-intensive technologies: drone fleets, satellite analysis, and continuous data fusion. Trustworthy AI principles identify environmental well-being as a core dimension, and Horizon Europe requires projects to integrate sustainability in digital innovation. BorderForce must monitor its environmental footprint to align with EU expectations on green AI development.</p> <p>Good practice mitigations across the lifecycle to address risks identified:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Pre-processing: Environmental considerations should be factored into system design choices, such as selecting energy-efficient hardware, optimising algorithms to reduce computational demands, and minimising reliance on high-emission processes. Life-cycle assessments of drones, sensors, and data storage should be carried out to anticipate energy and resource consumption.● In-processing: During operations, sustainability requires monitoring and managing resource intensity in real time.● Post-processing: After deployment, environmental sustainability depends on measuring and reporting the project's energy footprint. Periodic reviews should capture the cumulative impact of system operation, with results informing adjustments in hardware use, model efficiency, or cloud services.
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6. Responsible AI Assessment

The questionnaire was co-validated with input from partners involved in system development, legal compliance, and ethical oversight, to ensure that the questions are both grounded in regulatory expectations and adapted to the operational realities of the project. In addition to serving as an assessment tool, it creates a structured space for reflection, allowing partners to engage with the implications of their work beyond performance metrics or technical feasibility.

Ultimately, this methodological integration supports the core objective of Task 2.5: to enable a sandbox approach to AI development, where potential harms can be identified, debated, and mitigated in a controlled and anticipatory way. This is essential for ensuring that BorderForce follows responsible AI use in law enforcement contexts, where public trust and legal legitimacy are crucial.

To ensure that the insights gathered translate into actionable findings, the responses were analysed based on their alignment with the Trustworthy AI principles. First, each completed questionnaire was reviewed to assess the degree to which the system design, implementation, and deployment reflected the core dimensions of Trustworthy AI. Where relevant, the analysis also considered the consistency of responses across different partners. Discrepancies in how ethical or legal issues are interpreted may point to coordination challenges or knowledge gaps, and these findings inform our recommendations.

6.1 Privacy

The risk identification and mitigation strategy established that **good practice** in Privacy requires three things: narrowly defined and lawful collection parameters during pre-processing, strict enforcement of minimisation and accuracy during processing, and harmonised retention and deletion standards in the post-processing. The questionnaire responses show that while partners are aware of these requirements, practices remain uneven across components.

In the **pre-processing stage**, responses show that this benchmark is only partially met. Drone, mesh, multi-sensor, and satellite modules rely on visual data that may capture identifiable individuals, which places them under GDPR and LED obligations. Yet not all components specified a lawful basis for processing, even though this is a requirement under GDPR Article 6. This gap must be addressed by documenting the legal ground for each activity in the Data Management Plan.

Privacy was acknowledged in principle, but concrete minimisation measures were limited. Few partners reported using anonymised or synthetic datasets, which would reduce risks in the data-centric phase. OSINT modules were mentioned but approaches to filtering personal identifiers were inconsistent. This falls short of the benchmark for narrowly scoped collection and controlled inputs. Introducing automated PII detection or hybrid filtering would strengthen compliance with GDPR and help meet AI Act Article 9 expectations on risk management.

During the **in-processing stage**, good practice requires the strict enforcement of minimisation and accuracy. Responses suggest this is only partially achieved. Several components reported that irrelevant or redundant data will be deleted during operations, which shows awareness of GDPR Article 5(1)(c). However, the approaches described were inconsistent, and in some cases, minimisation appeared to rely on ad hoc practices rather than clearly defined procedures. OSINT modules were vague about how personal identifiers would be excluded in real time. This uncertainty creates a governance gap, as it is unclear how these safeguards will be applied consistently across all components. To align with the benchmark, BorderForce must ensure that minimisation and accuracy checks are not left to individual practice but are codified in operational rules.

During the **post-processing stage**, good practice requires harmonised governance of retention and deletion, even if different components have different operational needs. Responses confirm that heterogeneity is expected: some subsystems do not retain data beyond immediate use, while others plan longer-term storage for research or traceability purposes. This diversity can be compatible with GDPR, provided it is clearly justified and managed under project-wide standards. To ensure compliance with GDPR Article 5(1)(e) on storage limitation, each component must define retention periods that are proportionate to its function and document them

transparently. Where long-term or cloud-based storage is foreseen, anonymisation and secure deletion procedures should also be in place, in line with GDPR Article 32.

The analysis shows awareness of privacy requirements but falls short of full compliance in several areas. Lawful bases for processing are not consistently defined, minimisation measures are not applied uniformly, OSINT filtering lacks clarity, and retention practices are fragmented. Addressing these gaps through **clearer documentation, harmonised governance standards, and consistent safeguards** will enhance the legitimacy and reliability of the system.

6.2 Fairness

As seen in the previous section, the risk identification and mitigation strategy established that **good practice** in fairness requires three things: representative and unbiased datasets during pre-processing, systematic testing for bias during in processing, and ongoing monitoring of discriminatory outcomes in post-processing. The responses show that while partners are aware of these requirements, concrete practices remain uneven and only partially aligned with AI Act obligations.

At the **pre-processing stage**, good practice requires that datasets reflect the diversity of operational contexts without systematically excluding or over-representing particular groups. Among AI-based modules, few explicitly demonstrated mechanisms to ensure representativeness or prevent bias. Some partners acknowledged environmental or operational sources of bias and suggested partial mitigation measures, such as limiting data collection or applying strict access controls. While these measures indicate awareness, they fall short of Article 10(2) requirements to document data quality and representativeness. To align with good practice, all AI-driven components should conduct bias assessments of input data, expand dataset diversity, and document these steps in component-level governance plans.

At the **in-processing stage**, good practice requires that bias testing be conducted during development and operations to ensure that outputs remain consistent and equitable across contexts. Questionnaire responses suggest that this benchmark is only partially met: one analytical component indicated plans to test its detection models under varied environmental conditions, but others did not. This falls short of AI Act Article 10(3), which requires bias evaluation and performance validation during development. To address this, all AI-supported components must test and document behaviour under diverse conditions, to ensure that alerts and risk scores do not systematically disadvantage vulnerable groups. Infrastructure components, while not required to perform bias testing, should still enable traceability and transparency for AI modules, in line with AI Act Article 12.

Plans for **post-deployment** fairness monitoring are emerging, with some components foreseeing regular audits and feedback loops that allow operators to flag potential performance issues. This demonstrates an awareness of AI Act Article 9. Other components currently rely more heavily on user oversight, which provides an important baseline but may not capture issues systematically. Adopting harmonised monitoring procedures, which may include logs of alerts, review of outcomes, and documentation of corrective actions, would ensure that fairness is consistently evaluated across all modules. Infrastructure components will also be important here, as they can provide reliable logging and synchronisation to facilitate oversight.

Overall, BorderForce partners have already integrated several safeguards that reflect GDPR and AI Act requirements on fairness, including proportional data collection, access controls, and emerging plans for testing and monitoring. These measures provide a solid foundation. The main opportunities for strengthening compliance lie in **making dataset more representative, expanding testing protocols across components, and harmonising post-deployment monitoring.**

6.3 Explainability & Transparency

The risk identification and mitigation strategy established that good practice in explainability and transparency requires: defining user-oriented explanation needs at the design stage, integrating mechanisms that allow operators to understand outputs during operations, and establishing feedback loops to verify and improve the usefulness of explanations after deployment. Responses confirm that partners are aware of these requirements and have already introduced promising measures, but practices remain uneven across components.

At the **design stage**, several components already foresee user manuals, visual materials, or operational guidance to support operator understanding. These are encouraging steps that align with AI Act Articles 13 and 14, which require users to comprehend a system's purpose, logic, and limitations. However, not all components approach explainability in the same way. Some infrastructure modules assumed that explainability was unnecessary because their users are already familiar with the system. While this reflects operational reality, it creates a compliance risk, since the AI Act requires explainability to be demonstrable. To consolidate good practice, all components should include user-oriented documentation that clarifies how outputs are produced, what oversight mechanisms apply, and how uncertainty factors are managed.

In addition, several AI-driven components that generate detections or alerts already plan to provide contextual information **during operations**, such as confidence levels or provenance references, to help operators interpret results. This is well aligned with AI Act Article 13(2), which requires interpretability, and Article 14(4), which

mandates effective oversight. Nonetheless, other modules still rely on external documentation or partner interfaces for explanations. While this provides a useful baseline, embedding interpretability features directly into each component would strengthen accountability and ensure consistency across the system. Practical measures could include short textual explanations of outputs or displaying thresholds alongside alerts, so operators can understand both the result and the reasoning behind it in real time.

In the **post-processing stage**, to complement these operational safeguards, some components already plan to collect feedback from law enforcement operators on the usefulness and clarity of explanations. This is a positive step and fully consistent with AI Act Article 9 on continuous risk management. A recommendation in this area is to establish standardised feedback mechanisms, for example, structured surveys or periodic operator reviews. This would allow the project to capture recurring misunderstandings. This information could then be fed back into documentation, retraining cycles, or interface improvements, ensuring that explanations remain clear and relevant as the system evolves.

Taken together, these responses show that BorderForce partners have already made tangible progress in planning explainability measures, particularly through manuals, contextual outputs, and emerging feedback processes. These efforts provide a strong baseline for compliance with the AI Act. The next step is to consolidate these practices through **ensuring explainability is demonstrable for all components, embedding interpretability features directly into design, and harmonising user feedback processes.**

6.4 Accountability

Good practice in accountability requires that all components ensure traceability of inputs and outputs, robust logging mechanisms, and clear oversight and escalation procedures across the AI lifecycle. In pre-processing, this means embedding record-keeping into the architecture so that inputs, processing steps, and operator actions can be reconstructed if needed. During in-processing, operators must be able to understand and intervene in system behaviour, particularly when outputs are uncertain or low-confidence. In the post-processing phase, logs and audit trails must be accessible for internal and external oversight, ensuring that compliance is verifiable over time.

In the **pre-processing stage**, partners showed various levels of maturity in their accountability approach. The drone and mesh system includes a detailed plan to log every detection with unique identifiers, timestamps, and links to the original data, which is fully aligned with the Trustworthy AI principle of accountability and GDPR's accountability requirement (Article 5(2)). The satellite analysis component offers a straightforward link between outputs and input images, which can serve as

a useful starting point for traceability. By contrast, the C2 server and the multi-sensor platform mainly operate as data integration and storage modules rather than AI-driven decision-making components. While they are not subject to the AI Act, they remain responsible under GDPR Article 30 and the Data Governance Act to document processing activities and ensure that their logging mechanisms support the system's overall auditability.

During the **in-processing stage**, a good practice requires consistent accountability mechanisms during system operation, particularly for AI components generating detections, classifications, or alerts. The drone and mesh system provides the clearest safeguards by requiring operator verification of all detections, including low-confidence outputs. This is directly aligned with the AI Act's human oversight provisions (Art. 14) and the LED's prohibition of fully automated law enforcement decisions. Other AI modules, such as the multi-sensor platform, acknowledge operator involvement but provide less clarity on escalation procedures, leaving uncertainty about how accountability will be maintained in ambiguous cases.

For AI components, **post-processing** accountability requires comprehensive audit trails that can be accessed and reviewed by oversight bodies. The drone and mesh system meets this benchmark by logging every access to stored video data with user IDs, timestamps, and the actions performed, which is fully aligned with GDPR Article 30 and AI Act Article 12. Other AI modules did not provide equivalent detail in their responses, raising the need for more systematic logging frameworks.

Overall, BorderForce shows encouraging progress in embedding accountability, particularly within AI components such as the drone and mesh detection system. These measures are already aligned with GDPR, and AI Act provisions, though greater consistency is needed across the system. Non-AI infrastructure is not subject to AI Act rules but remains essential for supporting transparency and data governance obligations. To ensure full compliance, **the project should standardise accountability procedures across all modules, verify escalation mechanisms under operational conditions (for example, through failure simulations), and make sure audit trails are accessible for regular internal and external review.**

6.5 Safety & Security

The risk identification and mitigation strategy established that **good practice** in safety & security require three things: security by design and formal threat modelling during pre-processing, layered defences and operator safeguards during in-processing, and tamper-evident logging with regular verification during post-processing. The questionnaire responses show that partners have implemented strong foundational controls, but there are clear opportunities to strengthen consistency in systematic threat assessment, escalation procedures, and adversarial testing across components.

During the **pre-processing stage**, good practice requires security by design and formal threat modelling. Questionnaire responses show that this benchmark is only partially met. Partners describe defence-in-depth measures including restricted storage environments, role-based access control, encrypted transport, and in some cases fully offline operation. These align well with GDPR Article 32 requirements for appropriate technical and organisational security measures and contribute to AI Act Article 15 obligations for AI modules. Yet not all components have documented formal threat modelling or acceptance criteria for robustness at component level. This gap must be addressed by establishing what attacks are in scope, what mitigations apply, and how residual risk is judged acceptable. A project-wide threat model and minimum control baseline would close this gap and make protections comparable across components.

During the **in-processing stage**, good practice requires layered defences and clear operator safeguards against manipulation or degraded performance. Questionnaire responses suggest this is only partially achieved. Partners plan or already use encrypted and authenticated command links, integrity checks, and operator verification of detections, which shows awareness of AI Act Article 15 expectations on resilience. However, the approaches described were inconsistent, and in some cases escalation procedures appeared to rely on ad hoc practices rather than clearly defined protocols. This uncertainty creates a governance gap, as it is unclear how safeguards will be applied consistently during live operations. To align with the benchmark, BorderForce must ensure that escalation thresholds and notification chains are codified in operational rules. Targeted tests against likely adversarial behaviours must be planned for AI modules, with results and mitigations formally recorded.

During the **post-processing stage**, good practice requires tamper-evident logging and regular verification of defences under stress or adversarial conditions. Questionnaire responses confirm that several components log access and actions and monitor for performance drift, and some include fail-safes such as return-to-base protocols. This demonstrates positive alignment with the benchmark. However, not all components have committed to periodic penetration testing, red-team exercises that simulate realistic attacks, or audits that check whether logs are complete. This diversity can be compatible with AI Act Article 15 and GDPR Article 32, provided it is clearly justified and managed under project-wide standards. To ensure compliance, each component must participate in a common schedule for security audits and cross-component exercises.

BorderForce demonstrates strong foundational controls in safety & security but falls short of full compliance in several areas. To address these gaps, **clearer documentation, harmonised governance standards, and consistent verification through red-teaming, penetration testing, and stress drills will enhance the legitimacy and reliability of the system.**

6.6 Environmental Sustainability

Good practice requires that environmental sustainability be factored into system design, operation, and monitoring. At the pre-processing stage, this means integrating energy-efficient hardware, optimised algorithms, and low-resource models. During in-processing, good practice involves minimising computational costs in real time, for example through optimised GPU use, transfer learning, or efficient system routing. In the post-processing phase, sustainability requires continuous monitoring and transparent reporting of energy consumption, with lessons from audits feeding back into improvements.

In the **pre-processing stage**, responses show that some components already factor in energy efficiency. The drone system and multi-sensor platform monitor power use for battery efficiency and storage. The satellite analysis component emphasises lightweight models to limit computational demand, while the C2 server highlights its inherently low resource footprint. Similarly, positive practices were also reported for reducing energy consumption **during operations**. Drone modules foresee optimised flight paths to conserve power, while the multi-sensor platform incorporates efficient GPUs. The satellite system makes use of lightweight model architectures, and transfer learning was mentioned to reduce training costs. These measures are aligned with expectations of efficiency during active use, though they remain fragmented across components and are not yet framed as a coordinated sustainability strategy.

Finally, at the **post-processing** stage, monitoring of environmental impacts after deployment remains limited and uneven. The drone system includes reviews of flight logs and ground station energy use, with the aim of refining charging schedules and improving battery management. The satellite component suggested possible measures for data centres, such as cable management to reduce cooling inefficiency, though these were described as options rather than confirmed practices. The C2 server emphasises its low footprint, while no specific monitoring was reported for the mobile tower or multi-sensor platform. Compared with the benchmark of systematic monitoring and transparent reporting, current practices are partial and lack standardisation. To move toward compliance with Horizon Europe and towards trustworthy AI, the consortium should establish **harmonised monitoring of energy consumption, document efficiency practices consistently, and report results during pilots**.

7. Next Steps

The preceding sections have outlined the system's alignment with the AI Act and complementary EU legislation, highlighting both strengths and areas for improvement across the six compliance principles. Each component demonstrates progress toward compliance regarding data privacy, fairness, explainability, and

accountability, while also revealing specific gaps that require action to meet the legal and ethical standards expected of high-risk AI systems.

The following section translates this analysis into a Matrix for Monitoring and Compliance, which consolidates the findings and identifies the actions already in place, as well as those requiring reinforcement or continuous oversight. This matrix serves as a practical tool to guide partners in maintaining compliance throughout the system’s lifecycle, ensuring that the obligations under EU legislation are systematically monitored, documented, and verifiable.

7.1 Matrix for monitoring and compliance

Table 3. Matrix for monitoring compliance

Trustworthy AI principle	Actions already in place to ensure trustworthiness	Actions to be reinforced / require monitoring
Privacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OSINT data used by HSE will be screened for sensitive biometric data. Only strictly relevant data will be captured, stored, or processed for the relevant component, unnecessary data will be deleted by all partners in compliance with GDPR, Art.5 and the LED Art. 20. In the post-processing stage data may not be stored at all in the case of GSH, or only for the shortest period as defined in legislation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All partners must establish a clear legal basis for processing to avoid risk of over-collection and weak justification for data use. Ensure that their data collection parameters are more strictly defined. Each partner should review their DMP entries to confirm that the lawful basis for processing is documented, and traceable. Each partner must specify and confirm data storage locations and demonstrate that appropriate technical and organisational safeguards (encryption, access control, audit logs) are implemented. Deletion and anonymisation procedures, though largely compliant,

		<p>require harmonisation across all partners.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Components involved in data collection by all partners and fusion by components developed by AIT, HSE, and GmbH must ensure that the datasets and pre-trained models feeding into AI-based functions are relevant, representative, and free from structural bias.• Partners must establish formal testing and validation protocols for AI-driven components to monitor fairness under different operational scenarios and to detect potential discriminatory effects. These evaluations should be documented and integrated into the system's data governance plan, ensuring traceability.• All components should adopt continuous monitoring and audit mechanisms to ensure fairness remains an active compliance objective throughout deployment.
<p>Fairness</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The fusion and detection modules apply operational protocols that limit data collection to what is necessary for mission objectives, enforce access controls, and rely on predefined data retention schedules.• The detection and analysis components have also introduced procedures for evaluating model performance. This includes internal testing for detection accuracy and error distribution, continuous monitoring for performance anomalies, and feedback loops that allow operators to report and review system outputs. These practices are consistent with AI Act Article 10(3), which requires testing and validation to identify and mitigate bias, and with the broader Trustworthy AI principle of fairness.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The detection and alert modules provide contextual information when a detection occurs, helping operators understand why an alert was generated. This• Infrastructure elements such as the GmbH C2 server and data fusion platform components by HSE should incorporate traceable data flow documentation and ensure
	<p>Transparency and Explainability</p>	

aligns with AI Act Articles 13(2) and 14(4).

that system logs are accessible for review.

- Additionally, command and visualisation interfaces are designed to provide operators with manuals, visual guides, or embedded instructions tailored to the operational context of law enforcement. These tools support interpretability during system use and correspond to the obligations under GDPR Article 13 and LED Article 12 to inform users about the logic involved in automated processing.
- Several components also plan to collect operator feedback to assess comprehension and improve the clarity of outputs, contributing to the continuous improvement and risk monitoring requirements outlined in AI Act Art. 9.
- HSE and AIT must ensure that AI-based modules that generate automated or semi-automated outputs must also provide contextual explanations, such as the logic behind pattern detection, confidence levels, and model limitations, so that users can interpret results accurately and intervene when necessary. This would address the transparency gap identified under AI Act Article 14 and GDPR Article 13.
- All components should participate in a standardised feedback and comprehension monitoring process, ensuring that explainability remains an operational objective. This process should document user understanding, identify recurring points of confusion, and feed results back into interface design and training materials to sustain compliance over time.

Accountability

- The drone and mesh system already requires operator verification for all detections, including low-confidence outputs.
- All components should operate under a shared accountability framework that clarifies roles, responsibilities, and procedures for unified audit trails and defined

Safety & Security

- The multi-sensor platform and C2 server foresee human involvement, either through operator verification (multi-sensor) or the possibility of manual override (C2). While these modules are not central AI systems, their design still embeds the principle that humans remain in control, which supports the GDPR accountability principle (Art. 5(2)) and reflects the AI Act's emphasis on meaningful human oversight.
- Components already apply security-by-design measures, including encrypted storage and transmission (AIT's Multi-Sensor Platform with TLS/SSL + MWTT), authenticated drone command links, role-based access, firewalls, and secure model storage. Several partners also perform manual dataset reviews and monitor performance metrics for anomalies. These measures align with GDPR Article 32 and AI Act Article 15.
- The multi-sensor platform and C2 server foresee human involvement, either through operator verification (multi-sensor) or the possibility of manual override (C2). While these modules are not central AI systems, their design still embeds the principle that humans remain in control, which supports the GDPR accountability principle (Art. 5(2)) and reflects the AI Act's emphasis on meaningful human oversight.
- ECOE, AIT and HSE should create a formal escalation pathway should be implemented to address low-confidence or anomalous detections, ensuring that these are reviewed promptly by authorised operators. This process would align with the AI Act's obligations on risk management (Art. 9) and human oversight (Art. 14).
- BorderForce partners must transition from isolated technical safeguards to a documented, system-wide risk management framework. This includes formal threat and hazard identification, structured evaluation of risks to fundamental rights, and validation of preventive controls like encryption and access management prior to deployment.
- A continuous post-deployment monitoring protocol by all partners must be established with clear accountability, and all risk-related activities must be logged and reviewed regularly.

Environmental Sustainability

- Several components integrate resource-efficiency measures, such as lightweight AI models, optimised GPU
- To align with Horizon Europe's sustainability criteria, the consortium should monitor and document energy

usage, adaptive battery management, and deployment on low-resource servers. These actions contribute to reducing the system's energy footprint.

consumption during pilots and operational phases, assessing variations across components and environments.

- Environmental performance indicators should be regularly reported and shared across the consortium.

After the matrix, one cross-cutting recommendation applies to all partners: Each organisation should designate a **Data Protection Officer (DPO)** or equivalent contact responsible for ensuring coherence across compliance activities. Some partners have not yet identified a clear contact point for data protection and ethical oversight. Establishing this role is essential for fulfilling GDPR and AI Act obligations, supporting coordination with supervisory authorities, and ensuring consistent application of safeguards across all components.

In conclusion, the measures outlined in this report aim to ensure that BorderForce remains both compliant and credible as a rights-respecting, accountable security system. Each component must meet the legal standards set by the AI Act, the GDPR, and related frameworks, allowing the platform to balance operational efficiency with the protection of individual rights. The proposed safeguards further strengthen proposed compliance within the system's architecture rather than treat it as an external requirement.

8. Annexes

8.1 Annex I: Questionnaire sent to the consortium

Impact Assessment Questionnaires

Instructions

This questionnaire is designed to collect partner inputs for Deliverable D2.4 under Task 2.5, supporting the preparation of AI sandbox assessments on data governance, privacy, trustworthy AI practices, and environmental considerations across BorderForce components.

It is organised around the main principles that are common to privacy, social, and environmental impact assessments. Within each principle, questions are then divided into the three main stages of AI development:

1. **Pre-processing assessment:** identifying the main routes to risks that can arise at this stage, in which the model is designed and planned. These routes include data collection, curation, and governance, as well as design choices about model architecture and objective function.
2. **In-processing assessment** evaluates to what extent the trained model exhibits risks, such as unequal performance across groups, unsafe or unreliable behaviour in certain contexts, or excessive resource demands. This stage considers whether these risks were identified and mitigated during development and assesses the effectiveness of such efforts.
3. **Post-processing assessment:** analysing how risks evolve once the model is deployed in real-world. Particular attention is paid to model drift, degradation of performance that may impact on sociotechnical risks, and emergent risks that were not apparent in pre or in-processing.

We kindly ask each partner to complete this questionnaire **as thoroughly as possible**. Providing more details, precise and tailored responses will lead to a better analysis and feedback. If you believe a question is not relevant for your use case, please indicate this.

Should you require any assistance while completing, please contact the ETICAS team for support.

We kindly ask technical partners to complete and send back the questionnaire.

General Information	
Partner name	Answer
Use case participation (PUC1–PUC4)	Answer
Component or activity you participate	Answer

Main contact in your org. (name, email)	Answer
DPO contact	Answer
Explain your role in the project, the decision your component supports, and what type of processing will you be involved in	Answer

Privacy and data governance

1. What type of data will be collected? Does it include any special categories such as biometric or sensitive personal data?

Answer

2. Explain how data will be collected and stored. Will synthetic or anonymized datasets be used?

Answer

3. If your component uses open-source intelligence (OSINT) sources, describe how you plan to filter or exclude personal identifiers from public data streams. Specify whether your approach includes automated PII detection, manual curation, or other filtering techniques.

Answer

4. Describe how you will ensure data quality and data minimization are integrated into your system by design. Specify any planned measures for reducing unnecessary data processing.

Answer

5. If your component processes live sensor feeds, drone data, or OSINT inputs in real time, explain how privacy safeguards will be applied while the system is operating.

Answer

6. How long will you retain data collected or generated by the system, and what deletion or anonymization mechanisms are in place?

Answer

Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

7. Building on your answer to Q1, is the data that you will collect representative of the populations involved and affected?

Answer

8. Have you identified potential sources of bias in the datasets (for ex. demographic imbalance, sampling gaps)?

Answer

Pre

In

Post

Pre

9. Have you identified any potential impacts of your component on the fundamental rights of individuals or communities? If yes, describe the rights potentially affected and any planned mitigation measures?

Answer

In

10. Are there plans to test the system for bias during development? If so, what strategies will be used?

Answer

Post

11. How will you monitor ongoing bias or discriminatory outputs once the system is deployed?

Answer

Transparency

Pre

12. Have you defined the specific explanation needs of police and LEA operators for your component (e.g., understanding risk scores, alerts, or system recommendations)?

Answer

In

13. How do you plan to integrate any mechanisms (e.g., interpretable models, post-hoc explainers, rule-based logic) that allow operators to understand why a specific decision or alert was generated?

Answer

Post

14. During pilots or initial deployment, how will you assess how LEA's operators understand the system's outputs (e.g., alerts, risk scores, or classifications)? Do you plan to collect feedback from operators on the usefulness, and reliability of the explanations provided by your component? If yes, describe the planned approach.

Answer

Accountability

Pre

15. Will your component include a way to track which inputs are used to generate outputs? If yes, explain how this will be captured to ensure AI-driven decisions can later be traced back.

Answer

In

16. Explain how human oversight will be maintained in decision-making processes. If the system generates uncertain or low-confidence outputs, what escalation mechanisms will be in place to ensure appropriate human intervention?

Answer

Post

17. Specify whether you plan to implement logging or audit trails for personal data access, modifications, or deletions to support traceability and accountability during and after deployment.

Answer

Safety and Security

Pre

18. Describe planned measures to ensure the security of data, models, and infrastructure (e.g., encryption, authentication, intrusion detection, disaster recovery).

Answer

In

19. During model training and operation, what measures are planned to prevent malicious prompt injections or manipulation? For example, will you implement context sanitization, input filtering, or other alignment controls to ensure the model only processes safe and authorized instructions?

Answer

Post

20. Will there be mechanisms to monitor performance degradation, manage adversarial attacks, or mitigate system failure?

Answer

Environmental Sustainability

Pre

21. Describe whether your component or infrastructure (e.g., sensors, data centers, model training) has mechanisms to monitor energy/resource consumption. If applicable, specify any planned optimizations to reduce energy/resource intensity.

Answer

In

22. Based on Q22, describe any planned measures to reduce environmental impact during training or operation (e.g., model reuse, transfer learning, optimizing GPU use).

Answer

Post

23. Once your component is deployed, how will you monitor and improve the system's energy efficiency during active service?

Answer

